

ADVANTAGES OF USING MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the benefits of using modern information technology in primary education.*

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According to the Ministry of Public Education, the total number of primary school students in our republic is 2,129,389. 111866 pedagogues have been teaching them. Nowadays, our state provides teachers with a creative approach to lessons, they are advanced in their work necessary measures have been developed and implemented in order to widely introduce pedagogical and information and communication technologies and to strengthen the foundation of students' initial knowledge acquisition, to increase their interest in mastering all subjects.

The current era places great demands on teachers and students the main requirements are the efficiency of the lesson, its quality, the knowledge and skills of the students, the various educational activities in schools, their organization, and the acquisition of various knowledge and skills by the students through it. Today, the role of innovative technologies, technical tools, including modern computers, in the correct and effective organization of the educational process is incomparable. Multimedia, animation, graphics, slides and the use of video films helps to make the lesson process more interesting, and for this, the teacher should work on himself and say to each lesson "how can I introduce something new into today's lesson process and make the lesson interesting?" he should ask himself questions, that is, he should avoid traditional education and try to provide non-traditional education.

It is known that education is a type of activity in which the teacher and students cooperate. as a result of receiving it, he will have the competencies to use it. In the process of learning new knowledge, it is natural for students to use different forms of mastering, for example, receiving information, processing it and putting it into practice. It takes place in processes such as implementation.

Nowadays, modern computers are used in general education schools it is not a secret to anyone that advanced pedagogic scientists have recognized that one of the most important indicators is the improvement of the possibilities of using technologies, the full use of modern technologies in the educational process. In particular, U.Sh. Begimkulov created a computer information environment that can meet the requirements of the present time in the educational process, as well as multimedia in the educational process, imitation in teaching, the necessary information on the computer offers to create a recommended database for input, systematization, storage and use using the technique.

Almost all secondary schools in our country are modern equipped with computer and telecommunication technologies. This, in turn, requires primary school teachers to have a new approach to their work. The introduction of new technologies into the educational process of elementary school classes, not to squeeze the teacher by technical means, but to change his task

and role through a new approach, based on a more lively, creative and creative approach to teaching activities turns into a profession.

When organizing the lesson process with the help of modern information technologies, the teacher should first:

- the purpose of the lesson;
- ways to achieve the goal;
- methods of presenting educational materials;
- teaching methods;
- types of educational assignments;
- questions for discussion;
- ways of organizing discussions and debates;
- it is necessary to identify factors such as methods of interaction and communication.

The use of computers and information technologies plays an important role in educating students to be intellectually and spiritually mature people, in developing their knowledge, skills and abilities in the essence of our national traditions and values, in learning the rich spiritual heritage of our great ancestors. Pedagogical staff and students will have the opportunity to receive, search, process and master a large amount of information through computer and information technology tools. Education, of course introduction of new pedagogical and information technologies in institutions. Conducting training sessions using new interactive methods, modern tools, i.e. information technology tools, including the use of multimedia in class sessions, the use of the Internet, will undoubtedly be effective.

Application of modern information technologies to primary education not only increasing the efficiency of training, but also the achievements of science independent and logical thinking, comprehensive by applying in practice it is of great importance in raising a well-rounded and highly moral person. For a teacher must be creative, he must prepare carefully for each lesson, should enter with novelty, because the sameness repeated in every lesson makes the student reduces interest in the lesson and science, as a result, the effectiveness of the lesson decreases will bring

The teacher uses modern computer technologies can perform several tasks:

- by using multimedia technologies in primary classes students develop interest in science;
- this method of education activates students' thinking abilities and increases the efficiency of learning material;
- provides an opportunity to model and visualize processes that are difficult or complex to demonstrate;
- assimilation of educational materials not only according to the level, but effective according to the level of logic and acceptance of students;
- students are given the opportunity to search for and find materials and find answers to problematic issues through independent research;
- conditions are created for students to master a new topic, solve examples, write essays, reports, get acquainted with educational materials, select and analyze information and data quickly.

Today, the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that, until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge and use teaches

them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to learn independently and to think, analyze, and even draw final conclusions by themselves. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance.

Applying modern information technologies to primary education not only increases the effectiveness of training sessions, but also plays an important role in educating an independent and logically thinking, well-rounded and highly moral person by applying the achievements of science in practice.

Every teacher must be creative, he is thorough in every lesson should be prepared and enter with novelty, because the sameness repeated in every lesson weakens the student's interest in the lesson and science, as a result, it leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of the lesson.

Important aspects of information technology for the teacher and student are as follows:

- ✓ focus the student's attention;
- ✓ expand the perception of information;
- ✓ inquisitiveness, creativity and independent activity;
- ✓ self-assessment.

Using information technologies in the teacher's activity the role of the lessons is reflected in the following:

- ✓ proper distribution of time;
- ✓ that the content of the educational material is bright and convincing provide;
- ✓ increase the amount of information provided;
- ✓ expanding the types of educational tasks;
- ✓ creation of healthy competition, creative environment;
- ✓ regular improvement of professional qualifications.

One of the most important things in the work of a teacher is to evaluate the knowledge of students. Control tests for various sections of all general education subjects are possible with the help of a computer.

Today, a special market of programs used as a didactic tool in the educational process is being formed in Uzbekistan. There are now many online programs that can be taken in general education classes. Among them, the first electronic textbooks are possible. Computer technology provides experience in a variety of interactive tasks.

For example, students can place events in chronological order, correctly interpret scientific terms and concepts, or correctly and they will be able to find out how they performed the tasks such as showing the terms and their meaning with an arrow on the left line or filling in the basic words of the given topic, completing test tasks, solving crossword puzzles, comparing them with the answers shown on the big screen with the help of multimedia. . During the lesson, the teacher uses the computer to present the existing materials in various forms: slides, video and audio clips, diagrams, tables, and musical forms. Computer the organization of the lesson process with the help of a strong influence on the imagination and memory of students, facilitates the process of remembering, turns the lesson into an interesting process, allows students to take part in one or another historical period and participate in the events.

Advanced pedagogical and new information from today's education teacher requires the use of technologies in the educational process. Lesson we present our thoughts and opinions on education by using interactive methods in our classes. We present our thoughts on the implementation of modern methods of teaching based on certain topics in primary classes.

"Video find" method - the following sequence of actions should be performed when using this method:

- several video clips are shown to the attention of students without comments, which help to illustrate the essence of the topic being studied;
- students explain what process is shown in each picture;
- record the nature of the processes in their notebooks;
- answer the questions asked by the teacher.

Based on this method, a video on the topic is shown through a computer. Students express their opinions about the topic of the video and the topic expressed in it.

Today, the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies allows them to search for the knowledge they acquire, independent study and thinking, analysis. even teaches them to draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance. Today, in education "Brainstorming", "Thoughtstorming", "Networks" method, "Sinquain", "BBB", "Fifth plus", "6x6x6", "Debate", "Role-playing game", Modern technologies such as FSMU, "Working in small groups", "Rounded snow", "Zigzag", "I will say the last word" are used.

It gives a positive result if it is used in lessons to repeat games and tasks or in reinforcement lessons. The choice of which type of game-task depends on the type of lesson, the level of training of students to perform games-tasks, their level of knowledge, opportunities for independent creative work, the ability to quickly recall what they have learned, and the degree to which creativity is formed. should be in education, attention is focused on the issue of teaching the student to think, to understand the opinion of others and to be able to express this opinion in oral and written form. takes place. The way of life and cultural creativity of the nation is studied on the basis of its rich historical heritage.

Today, the teacher is required to use advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in the educational process. Based on the above, based on our experiences, we present our thoughts on the ways of education by using interactive methods in the lessons. We think that it will provide practical help to our colleagues in increasing the effectiveness of training sessions. Also, he becomes one of the close assistants of students in fulfilling the responsible task of choosing their own direction and forming the skills of preparation for independent life. Below we give recommendations on the implementation of modern methods of teaching based on certain topics in the class section. You use it in a creative way and try to find an answer to the question of our first president: "What are we doing today to instill in our children a sense of pride, pride, and devotion to our motherland, which is sacred for every age"[1], - we hope that you will contribute to achieving the intended goal by implementing modern methods of education and upbringing.

In conclusion, the use of modern information and communication technologies in primary grades helps students to think independently, expand their creative research and logical thinking, connect what they learned in classes with life, and increase their interest in the lesson. From the conditions created on the basis of such modern requirements of teachers effective use and organization of lessons on the basis of advanced pedagogical and information communication technologies guarantees the quality of the educational process.

It is worth saying that as a result of using multimedia applications in every lesson students develop independent and creative thinking. As a conclusion, it can be said that the use of information and communication tools in primary school classes serves to increase the quality and efficiency of the lesson.

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